

Research

An Analysis of the Safety and Occupational health in Oil and Gas Drilling sites in Yemen

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Abstract: Occupational health has been defined as "enabling people to engage in their occupation in a way that causes the least harm to their health," but the World Health Organization has attempted to broaden this definition, stating that "health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing, not simply the absence of disease or infirmity." Putting employees' health first is certainly the most important factor in achieving a productive and efficient workplace culture; this has been shown to increase efficiency and improve employee mental health. Energy has evolved as a vital strategic resource for national development, given the fast-increasing global economy and urgent social requirements. Despite the efforts of various countries to develop renewable energy sources such as wind, nuclear, hydro, and solar, petroleum and natural gas continue to dominate global energy consumption. The goal of this study is to look at the current standards of occupational health and safety in Yemeni oil and gas drilling projects.

Keywords: Safety Culture; Safety Concept; Oil and Gas Drilling sites; Yemen

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Accepted: 24 May, 2022; **Published:** 31 May, 2022

How to cite this article: Taha Omar Yaaqob Alssarhi; Zhao Dong; Jourge Shovon Biswas (2022). An Analysis of the Safety and Occupational health in Oil and Gas Drilling sites in Yemen. *North American Academic Research*, 5(5), 11-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6604244>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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1.1 Aim of Research

The goal of this study is to look at the current occupational health and safety requirements in Yemeni oil and gas projects and compare them to worldwide best practices, especially the standards.

1.2 Background and Significance

With worldwide economy quickly develops further friendly requirements, energy has turned into a significant key asset for public turn of events. Albeit numerous nations are putting forth incredible attempts to foster practical energy like breeze, atomic, hydro and sun oriented, without a doubt, petrol petroleum gas overwhelm in worldwide energy requests. It is notable that the USA is the world's biggest oil customer, and it is additionally the biggest oil-bringing in country. As of late, the U.S. government is pushing and pulling the turn of events and examination of new energy and practical energy, which likewise makes oil utilization in the United States has declined, nonetheless, in around the world, requests of petrol and petroleum gas are filling quickly in a few arising agricultural nations, because of their fast monetary development, like China, Brazil and India.

Because of boring stage has normal for high gamble, all of petrol organizations have a typical view - security first, apply high solid hardware, embrace improved frame structure plan, and lay out wellbeing the executives guidelines to control and alleviation hazard and risk, in any case, these security offices and security frameworks could not accomplish fundamental security. Assuming a penetrating stage or a boring organization seeks after condition of fundamental security, it should have a brilliant wellbeing society. Security culture is one of the significant images of the advanced penetrating apparatuses and boring organization's wellbeing the executives development, it is a significant piece of security the board, and is additionally a type of safe qualities.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Safety

During the advancement of human culture, wellbeing has turned into the most essential condition for individuals to get by and create, which is as whole human agreement. The expression of security has a complete significance; as a rule, wellbeing implies that overall independence from risk, hazard, or danger of damage, injury, or misfortune to faculty and additionally property, whether caused purposely or unintentionally. On the perspective of designing to make sense of wellbeing, security implies ascertainable gamble does not surpass as far as possible, alleged risk alludes to ascertainable gamble of the likelihood of event and damage surpass suitable breaking point. On the perspective of work to make sense of wellbeing, security implies that functioning staff ought to keep away from inadmissible gamble, or injury or demise of faculty, the state or state of the property is lossless.

In various financial circumstances, wellbeing needs are unique. The more evolved society and economy, satisfactory degree of chance is lower, thusly requesting more wellbeing prerequisites. In synopsis, wellbeing implies that condition of human brain science, wellbeing, gear, and climate is not imperiled by outer gamble factors.

2.2 Safety Awareness

Individuals' wellbeing mindfulness is exceptionally perplexing, and everybody's security mindfulness state is unique. According to the perspective of the human's wellbeing portrayal to bunch into three kinds, specifically crisis, backhanded, prevalent security mindfulness. An overview of the safety awareness is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Safety awareness in Oil and gas industry

1. **Crisis wellbeing mindfulness:** Emergency security mindfulness implies that peril factors are self-evident, and they can straightforwardly cause risk and injury. For these dangers, laborers can rapidly identify, and 12 go to pressing lengths to keep away from them. Such wellbeing mindfulness depends on unconstrained, sense response.
2. **Roundabout security mindfulness:** Indirect wellbeing mindfulness mostly reflected in secret risk factors. Laborers can deliberately go to safe defensive lengths (like confinement and cautioning tape) to keep away from dangers and risks. The perilous outcomes stowed away are hard to be distinguished without security instruction and preparing.
3. **Unrivaled security mindfulness:** It alludes that specialist can go to preventive lengths to dispose of risk factors which are in an idle state, and not arise any impacts. This sort of security mindfulness is a general high necessity.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Design

This study adopted the Online Survey Research Design. It was deemed appropriate for this study, Researcher said that it is a design which studies a population through a sample in order to determine the status of a given phenomenon. Furthermore, research pointed out that the design collects relatively large data at a given time, and it is essentially cross-sectional because it is interested in the statistics that result when data are abstracted from a number of individual cases. Finally, related research that it describes a particular state of affairs at a given time and draws inferences from the sample group, using appropriate statistical technique. Therefore, since the study made use of the online questionnaire, which was distributed among the respondents, the Online Survey design was seen as meeting the necessary requirement for the study.

3.2 Research Case

Yemen Total Offshore Rig is a leader in deep-water drilling and can provide drilling services in petroleum and natural gas exploration. Yemen Total Offshore has thirty semisubmersibles, seven jack-ups, and one drillship in its fleet of offshore drilling rigs. In addition, four ultra-deep-water drill ships and two deep-water semisubmersibles are being built. Its service idea is that the assignment is to outperform the customer's expectations and consistently raise the bar, as well as 37 Yemen Total Offshore aids its customers in their endeavors to locate and produce offshore petroleum resources in the global area.

3.3 Sample size and Analysis

The total population of the study is 30 respondents comprising of all workers in private organizations in the oil and gas drilling sector. Adeniyi [4] defines population as the total number of large habitations of people in one geographical area, it often connotes all the members of the target of the study as defined by the aims and objectives of the study. Due to few numbers of the respondents, the entire population was used, which is the entire 30 respondents.

Data was collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics essentially involves the computation of simple frequency and percentage to describe the demographic information and to answer research questions and presented in a tabular form for discussion.

3.4 Data Collection and validation

The data for the study will be collected from two main sources namely: Primary Source and Secondary Source. This represents the main source of data used for the research. The primary data were obtained from questionnaires

issued by personal on-site interactions in addition to online interviews/interactions with the respondents. The questionnaires were quite simple to read and understand, this helped facilitate participation of the respondents especially the workers. In order to ensure the validity of the questionnaires, they were designed in a simple and straight forward manner, they are easy to read and respond to. The questionnaire was issued online. The questionnaire was carried out using the Likert 5-point scale.

3.5 Survey Questions

1. As an individual with experience at oil and gas drilling sites in Yemen, would you say good health and safety practices were being upheld?
2. While on site, would you say you were provided with sufficient personal protective equipment?
3. Would you say sufficient training was provided to employees?
4. Would you say nonprofessional workers/laborers have a good understanding of health & safety and their rights?
5. Would you say the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in Yemen?

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Results

Five research questions as stated in section 3.5 were answered based on analysis of data in line with the respondents' responses to the questionnaire items. All the responses were analyzed using the mean scores obtained from the Five-point Likert scale questionnaire used for the collection of the data. For better understanding and clear interpretation, the data were grouped into agreed and disagreed and the grand mean scores formed the basis for final decision on each of the research questions.

Figure 2: Graphical representations of response to question one.

Figure 2 presents the responses to research question one. In response to question 1, a total of (6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that good health and safety practices are being upheld at Oil and gas construction drilling sites in Yemen, (20%) respondents agree that good health and safety practices are being upheld at construction sites in Yemen, (31%) represents the respondents who neither agree nor disagree on the motion, (3%) of the respondents

strongly disagreed while 12 of the respondents representing 40% disagreed. The figure above reveals that majority of the respondents 40% representing 12 respondents disagreed that good health and safety practices are being upheld at oil and gas construction drilling sites in Yemen

Figure 3: Graphical representations of response to question two

Figure 3 presents the responses to research question two. In response to question 2, a total of (3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that sufficient personal protective equipment was provided while on site in Yemen, (31%) respondents agree that sufficient personal protective equipment was provided while on site in Yemen, (20%) represents the respondents who neither Agree or disagree on the motion, (0%) of the respondents strongly disagreed while 14 of the respondents representing 46% disagreed. From the above figure, it means that majority of the respondents 46% representing 14 respondents disagreed that sufficient personal protective equipment was provided while on site in Yemen.

Figure 4: Graphical representations of response to question three

Figure 4 presents the responses to research question three. In response to question 3, a total of (6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that sufficient training was provided to employees while on site in Yemen, (14%) respondents agree that sufficient training was provided to employees while on site in Yemen while on site in Yemen, (20%) represents the respondents who neither Agree or disagree on the motion, (9%) of the respondents strongly disagreed while 16 of the respondents representing 51% disagreed. From the above table, it means that majority of the respondents 51% representing 16 respondents disagreed that sufficient training was provided to employees while on site in Yemen.

Figure 5: Graphical representations of response to question four

Figure 5 presents the responses to research question four. In response to question 4, a total of 1 (3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that nonprofessional workers/laborers have a good understanding of health & safety and their rights in Yemen, (6%) respondents agree that nonprofessional workers/laborers have a good understanding of health & safety and their rights in Yemen, (17%) represents the respondents who neither Agree or disagree that nonprofessional workers/laborers have a good understanding of health & safety and their rights in Yemen, (23%) of the respondents strongly disagreed while 16 of the respondents representing 51% disagreed with the statement. The results from the above figure shows that majority of the respondents 51% representing 16 respondents disagreed that nonprofessional workers/laborers have a good understanding of health & safety and their rights in Yemen.

Figure 6: Graphical representations of response to question five

Figure 6 presents the responses to research question five. In response to question 5, a total of (9%) of the respondents strongly agreed the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in oil and gas construction drilling sites in Yemen, (20%) respondents agree that the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in Yemen construction, (25%) represents the respondents who neither Agree or disagree that the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in Yemen construction, (6%) of the respondents strongly disagreed that the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in Yemen construction while 12 of the respondents representing 40% disagreed the government has done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in oil and gas construction drilling sites in Yemen.

4.2 Discussion

The results from most interviews suggest that knowledge and skills of people planning and executing construction projects, work of the construction industry, cost of safety implementation and safety in the oil and gas drilling industry. Based on the specific objectives and research questions used for the study, the following were the major findings of the study:

1. Good health and safety practices are not being upheld at oil and gas drilling sites in Yemen
2. Sufficient personal protective equipment was not provided for workers while on site
3. Sufficient training was not provided to employees while on site
4. Nonprofessional workers/laborers don't have a good understanding of health & safety
5. The government has not done enough in the pursuit of good occupational health and safety practices in Yemen oil and gas drilling sites.

5. Conclusion

The importance attached to the safety of workers on construction sites can never be overemphasized. This is due to the occurrence of accidents on sites result in far reaching consequences like delays in project completion time, alter overall cost of executing project, taint the reputation of the drilling firm, de-motivate the co-workers and in some cases lead to death. This research revealed that Yemeni drilling workers lack safety consciousness in their practice, it further

revealed that the workers do not get adequate training before they start work. The longer years spent on site, the fewer amounts of accidents experienced by the workers, it was however observed that the older workers had more awareness of their rights and privileges this having to do largely with their educational background.

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